

Mapping Greenhouse Gas emissions from the food supply chains in France

Anna TRAORE^(a), Onrawee LAGUERRE^(a), Yosr ALLOUCHE^(b,c), Anthony DELAHAYE*^(a)

^(a) Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, FRISE
92761, Antony, France

^(a) International Institute of Refrigeration, 177 boulevard Malesherbes
75017 Paris, France

^(c) Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Trondheim, 7491, Norway

*Corresponding author: anthony.delahaye@inrae.fr

ABSTRACT

Agri-Food systems are responsible for 31% of the global emissions. Food systems generate mainly carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide, and F-gases. This study takes part of the European project Enough (n° 101036588) that aims to provide tools and methods to contribute to the EU Farm to Fork strategy to achieve climate neutral food businesses by 2050. In the current paper, an evaluation of emissions for France from 1990 to 2019 was carried out in order to build a database and identify the highest emitting food chain sectors in the country. The considered sectors are those at post-farm gate including processing, packaging, transport, retail, and consumption. Data is available in different inventories, using different methodologies, making them difficult to compare. In this study, the French governmental statistics have been used and indicated that retail is the largest emitting sector due to refrigerant leakages (direct emissions). These data were found to be in good agreement with those provided by FAO emissions-database for France. In terms of indirect emissions (energy consumption), transport was found to be the largest emitting sector. In terms of commodities, the carbon footprint of meat was found to be around 38001 kilotons CO₂eq. The established French database has been also compared to that of some selected European countries (Italy, Norway, United-Kingdom, and Germany). The findings indicated that Norway has the lowest emissions rate.

Keywords: greenhouse gas emissions, food supply chain, cold chain, database

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to climate change, several measures, regulations and research projects have been introduced in Europe to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (GHG). In order to achieve the GHG reduction targets, it is first necessary to have a rigorous knowledge of the current GHG emission trend. To do this, an assessment of past and current levels of GHG emissions is required. In addition, it has been reported that food systems are responsible for 31% of global GHG emissions (FAO, 2021d), mainly carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and refrigerant leakage from cold equipment. This large share justifies the interest in assessing the environmental impact related to the food supply chain.

This article aims at presenting the GHG emissions caused by the food supply chain in France from 1990 to 2019. To assess accurately those emissions, the supply chain has been segmented in different sectors: production, processing, packaging, transport, retail and consumption. The evaluation of these emissions is mainly based on governmental data and the FAO methodology presented by Tubiello et al. (2021).

2. METHODOLOGY

These GHG emissions data related to food supply chain and cold chain in France and some other countries have been extracted from the FAOSTAT database (statistical tool from FAO) which presents the GHG emissions by sector and by country. In addition, FAOSTAT generates the data of production, imports and exports of food products for each country.

2.1. Food chain emissions

GHG emissions generated by the food chain can be found in the “climate change” domain of FAOSTAT, while the emission data by sector is found in the sector “emissions shares”. The emissions shares are presented for each country, thereby, the data for France and for some other countries have been extracted for comparison purposes.

The FAO emission data were verified by comparing with the ones calculated by Eq. (1) as below (Tubiello et al., 2021).

$$\text{Emissions} = A \times F \times E \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

With A: activity data (TJ); F: food share (%) and E: emission factor (kg CO₂/TJ)

Table 1 presents a definition on these terms.

Table 1. Meaning of the terms of the equation 1

Term	Meaning
Activity data	Energy consumption (In the case of processing for example, it is the energy use in food and tobacco manufacturing.)
Food share	In the case of processing, it is the share of energy used to process food only compared to the energy used in all processing industries
Emission factor	CO ₂ emissions generated by 1 TJ of energy used

Table 2 summarizes the data sources to apply to Eq. 1 to estimate the food chain emissions in France.

Table 2. Summary of the data sources necessary to estimate the food chain emissions in France

Sector	Concerned activity	Food share	Emission factor
Processing	Final energy consumption by manufacturing of food and tobacco (UNSD Energy Statistics Database, transaction 1214F)	We assume that the share of energy used to process food is 100% (The one used for tobacco processing is negligible)	Default emission factor of IPCC
Packaging	We consider the energy required to manufacture packaging materials used in food industries.		The electricity factor comes from IEA
	For plastic and glass: Final energy consumption by non-metallic minerals (UNSD Energy Statistics Database, transaction 1214B)	19% of the energy consumed for glass production is dedicated to food packaging. 0,48% of the energy used in chemical industries serves to manufacture plastic food packaging.	
	For paper: Final energy consumption by paper, pulp and print (UNSD Energy Statistics Database, transaction 1214G)	Calculated from production data of FAOSTAT: The share corresponds to the production of paper material used in food industries over the overall paper production.	

	For tin: UNSD industrial commodity statistics database	Calculated by dividing the tin production by the total iron production. Thus, we consider that all the tin is used for food packaging.	
	For aluminium: International Aluminium Institute	The percentage is in the range 2%, 27%	
Transport	Values of EDGAR-FOOD		
Retail	Final energy consumption by commercial and public services (UNSD Energy Statistics Database, transaction 1235)	Food retail requires 11% of the energy consumed by shops and public services.	Default emission factor of IPCC
Domestic consumption	Final energy consumption by households (UNSD Energy Statistics Database, transaction 1231)	6% of domestic energy consumption is for cooking and 4% for refrigeration. So, the food share is 10% for domestic energy consumption.	The electricity factor comes from IEA

2.2. Cold chain emissions

Like the food chain, the cold chain is composed of different sectors: processing, transport, storage, retail, and consumption. The GHG emissions data are available in the IIR database (Sarr et al., 2021). In addition to France, the emissions of other countries have also been extracted for comparison.

2.3. Food production

Previously, data were classified by sector and now for the analysis of the emissions of different products, we will be interested in production import and export data of meat. The production data are available in the domain "production" and the sector "crops and livestock products" and the import and export data in the sector "crops and livestock products" in the domain "trade" and are used in the result section.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Food production in France

Fig. 1 shows the production of all food products in France from 1990 to 2020.

Figure 1. Food production in France from 1990 to 2020 (FAO, 2021b)

Figure 2. Food production in France from 1990 to 2020 (FAO, 2021b)

From 1990 to 2015, there has been a slight increase in food production in France. This could be explained by the increase in population and the higher technology performances. After 2015, the production decreases slightly. Among the various socio-economic explanations, this could be the result of the modification of consumer behaviour, i.e. less food consumption due to dietary concerns and new sources of proteins.

3.2. Emissions caused by the food supply chain in France

Fig. 2 presents GHG emissions from the food supply chain in France for different sectors from 1990 to 2019. From 1990 to 2010, 40% increase is noticed from 5×10^4 to $8,6 \times 10^4$ kilotons CO₂eq. Afterwards, 20% of emissions drop was observed in 2019 (to $6,5 \times 10^4$ kg CO₂eq). The share of GHG emissions from food retail is the most significant (except for 1990) and sets the trend for overall emissions (all sectors combined).

Figure 3. Contribution of each sector to global emissions from food supply chain in France from 1990 to 2019 (FAO, 2021a)

Fig. 3 shows the emissions of several GHG in food supply chain in France from 1990 to 2019. The gases emitted are mainly carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and F-gases generated by refrigerant leakage which have the highest Global Warning Potential (GWP).

CO₂ is the most emitted gas and the emission is nearly constant over 1990-2019. CH₄ and N₂O are also almost constant but the emission is more than 5 times lower than that of CO₂. The F-gases emissions increased from 1990 to 2010 and then decreased until 2019. This decrease could be explained by the establishment of regulations driving to low GWP refrigerants. The obligation of energy class labels on equipment and the measures to reduce food loss and wastes are complimentary ways to reduce GHG emissions ("LOI n° 2018-938 du 30 octobre 2018 pour l'équilibre des relations commerciales dans le secteur agricole et alimentaire et une alimentation saine, durable et accessible à tous (1)," 2018) - for balanced trade relations in the agricultural and food sector and healthy, sustainable food accessible to all). It is to be emphasized that FAO considered F-gases only due to refrigerant leakage in the retail sector, the ones from other sectors were not taken into account because of the lack of data.

Figure 4. Contribution of each greenhouse gas to the emissions of the Food supply chain in France from 1990 to 2019 (FAO, 2021a)

Fig. 4 summarizes the GHG emissions in different sectors of the food cold chain in France in 2017 related to the electricity consumption, refrigerant leakage and gasoil consumption. Transport is the most emitting sector in the cold chain due to a high demand in gasoil, while the retail is the most emitting sector considering the food supply chain.

Figure 5. Carbon footprint of the food cold chain in France in 2017 (Sarr et al., 2021)

3.3. Comparison of GHG emissions from food supply chain in Europe

Fig. 5 presents the GHG emissions from food supply chains in France, Italy, Norway, UK and Germany from 1990 to 2019. The emissions in France and in Italy are almost the same, with an increase of the emissions from 1990 to 2010, followed by a decrease from 2010 to 2019. On the contrary, for UK, the emissions are stable over the same period, and always lower than those of France and Italy. This trend cannot be explained by the difference in population between the three countries, which are comparable. The emissions are the highest in Germany and the lowest in Norway. It is important to highlight that Germany has the largest population and uses mainly coal for its electricity production.

Figure 6. Carbon footprint of the food supply chain in France, Italy, Norway and United-Kingdom from 1990 to 2019 (FAO, 2021a)

The GHG emissions due only to the cold chain in the same countries are compared (Fig. 6). As for the supply chain, the food cold chain in Germany is the most emitting. For all countries, the transport sector emitted the most. A more detailed analysis led to the conclusion that in all these countries, the cold chain emissions are mainly indirect emissions due to electricity and gasoil consumption. When emissions from gasoil are not considered, lower emissions in France and Norway can be explained by the low carbon footprint technology for energy production.

Figure 7. Carbon footprint of the food cold chain in France, Italy, Norway, United-Kingdom and Germany in 2017 (Sarr et al., 2021)

3.4. Revaluation of FAO emissions

To assess the correctness of the FAO calculation, only the CO₂ emissions have been considered in this section because this gas contributes the most to the environmental impact. The assessment of emissions has been undertaken for 2013, 2015, 2017 and 2019 because of the available of activity data for these years.

3.4.1. Processing

Table 3 presents the emissions due to food processing in France. The emissions from the FAOSTAT database are compared to the calculated emissions values (Eq. 1). The differences vary from 0,967 to 15,73% (Table 3).

Table 3. Verification of CO₂ emissions from the food processing sector in France

Year	FAO value (kilotons CO ₂)	Calculated value (kilotons CO ₂)	Difference (%)
2013	10024	9927	0,967
2015	10525	10156	3,505
2017	10526	10064	4,389
2019	11220	9455	15,73

3.4.2. Food packaging

The calculation of emissions due to food packaging was undertaken only for 2013 and 2015 because of the availability of activity data for these years. The comparison between the calculated and the FAO values shows the difference of about 30% (Table 4). This difference could be due to: (i) the difference in the packaging materials considered in our calculation (cf. Table 2, concerned activity: plastic, glass, paper, tin and aluminium) and in FAO data; (ii) the food share considered in our calculation (cf. Table 2, food share) and FAO data.

Table 4. Verification of CO₂ emissions from the food packaging sector in France

Year	FAO value (kilotons CO ₂)	Calculated value (kilotons CO ₂)	Difference (%)
2013	4166	3017	27,58
2015	4292	2844	33,73

3.4.3. Transport

Table 5 presents these data in comparison with the ones from EDGAR-FOOD database and the difference in the emissions of about 28% was observed. It was not clearly stated in FAOSTAT database how transport emissions were estimated. The difference could be due to the definition of distance travelled: a combination of the national distance within the country and of the proportion of the international distance crossing the country.

Table 5. Verification of CO₂ emissions from the food transport sector in France

Year	FAO value (kilotons CO ₂)	EDGAR-FOOD value (kilotons CO ₂)	Difference (%)
1990	17359	12501	27,98
2000	20147	14637	27,35
2010	18725	13333	28,79

3.4.4. Retail

Table 6 summarises the emissions due to food retail in France extracted from FAO database and the calculated values. A difference of less than 6% was observed.

Table 6. Verification of CO₂ emissions from the food retail sector in France

Year	FAO value (kilotons CO ₂)	Calculated value (kilotons CO ₂)	Difference (%)
2013	9139	8625	5,62
2015	8441	8059	4,52
2017	8582	8356	2,63
2019	7889	8088	2,52

3.4.5. Household Consumption

The emissions from the domestic food consumption have been calculated and compared with the FAO database (Table 7). The differences varies from 13 to 18%.

Table 7. Verification of CO₂ emissions from the food consumption sector in France

Year	FAO value (kilotons CO ₂)	Calculated value (kilotons CO ₂)	Difference (%)
2013	8182	9283	13,46
2015	6837	7821	14,39

2017	6901	8089	17,20
2019	6513	7710	18,38

3.5. Focus on the most GHG emitting products in France

According to Camanzi et al. (2017), products with the highest emissions in Europe are:

- Meat (38% of emissions)
- Meat and dairy products (17,3% of emissions)
- Bread and cereals (11,4% emissions)

In this paper, we evaluated GHG emissions only for cattle meat in France.

Fig. 7 shows the production and consumption data of cattle meat in France from 1990 to 2019, these data have been extracted from FAOSTAT database (FAO, 2021b) and Agreste (Ministerial statistical office of the French Ministry of Agriculture and Food, (Agreste, 2021)), respectively. To verify the data reliability, the consumption data from Agreste have been compared with the ones from FranceAgrimer (National Farm and Seafood Establishment, (FranceAgriMer, 2022)). The slight difference of 0,15% leads to consider that these data are reliable.

Figure 8. Production and consumption of cattle meat in France from 1990 to 2019 (FAO, 2021b), (Agreste, 2021) and (FranceAgriMer, 2022)

Fig. 8 presents the imports and exports of cattle meat in France extracted from the FAOSTAT database.

Figure 9. Imports and exports of cattle meat in France from 1990 à 2019 (FAO, 2021c)

The verification of the reliability of FAO data presented in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 was undertaken by a balance equation below:

$$\text{Production} + \text{Import} - \text{Export} = \text{Consumption} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Table 8. Verification of the reliability of FAO imports and exports data

Year	Consumption from Agreste (tons)	Calculated consumption using imports and exports from FAO (tons)	Calculated consumption using imports and exports from Idele and CNE (tons)
2010	1645259	1459068	1643258
2019	1546750	1346680	1529460

The non-respected balance leads to a question of reliability of the import and export data from FAO. Another source of import and export data from Idele and CNE (Idèle & CNE, 2019) were applied to the balance equation and only 1% difference between the left and the right terms was found. Thus, we can consider that Idele and CNE import - export data are more reliable (Fig. 9).

Figure 10. Imports and exports of cattle meat in France from 1990 à 2019 (Idèle & CNE, 2019)

From production in farm to consumption, cattle meat accounts for 35.8 kg CO₂eq / kg consumed in 2016 (ADEME, 2016) and each living animal emits 11.9 kg CO₂eq (Idèle, 2015). If the GHG emissions of food supply chain (from processing to consumption) is considered (production in farm not included), we can consider 23,9kg CO₂eq / kg consumed. The overall emissions can be calculated by multiplying this factor by the consumption of meat. Fig. 10 shows meat consumption in different years from 1990 to 2021 (Agreste). Based on this figure, the consumption in 2016 has been estimated at 1,59 × 10⁶ tons and 38001 kilotons CO₂eq emitted.

Figure 11. Evolution of cattle meat consumption in France since 1990 (Agreste, 2021)

4. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

This article aims at evaluating GHG emissions generated by the food supply chains in France and Europe. These emissions have been extracted from the FAOSTAT database and revaluated following Tubiello et al. (2021) methodology. First, the emissions were presented by sector of the food chain and the results showed that the retail is the most emitting sector. Then, the emissions of the cold chain have been investigated and it was found that the transport is the most emitting due to huge consumption of gasoil. To finish, emissions of cattle meat have been evaluated and it has been discovered that 38001 kilotons of CO₂eq have been emitted by the cattle meat chain. A perspective would be to study the impact of other food products.

ABREVIATION

ADEME	Ecological Transition Agency
Agreste	Ministerial statistical office of the Ministry of Agriculture and Food
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
FranceAgriMer	National Establishments of Agricultural and Seafood Products
Idèle	Livestock Institute
IEA	International Energy Agency
IIR	International Institute of Refrigeration
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GWP	Global Warning Potential
UNSD	United Nations Statistics Division en anglais

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